

Molecular Insight into the Ternary Complex Formation between Ethambutol, Isoniazid and β -Cyclodextrin

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Abstract

Long term intake of antituberculosis drugs will lead to severe adverse reactions that will ultimately deteriorate a patient's health and well-being. With that, the ternary inclusion complex was explored, whereby β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) was chosen as the supramolecular host carrier to accommodate two kinds of first line antituberculosis guest drug molecules simultaneously, namely isoniazid (INH) and ethambutol (ETB) which would provide many therapeutic benefits. The inclusion complex of β -CD/INH/ETB was prepared using solvent evaporation method. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy ($^1\text{H-NMR}$), and 2-dimensional nuclear Overhauser effect spectroscopy (2D-NOESY) NMR were used to investigate the functional groups and structure of the complex. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) were employed to study the surface morphology and crystallinity changes during complex formation. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed to investigate the thermal properties of the complex. FT-IR and both types of NMR results had revealed the successful penetration of both the drug molecules into the β -CD cavity. SEM images and XRD spectra had shown a drastic change in surface structure and reduction in crystallinity during complex formation, which had indicated successful formation of a new compound. TGA had proven that the complex had significantly greater thermal stability as compared to the pure components. Molecular dynamics (MD) and molecular docking simulations were also performed to understand the molecular interaction between β -CD, INH, and ETB. Through precise calculations of interaction and binding energies, β -CD/INH/ETB was found to be a more stable inclusion complex compared to the binary β -CD/INH and β -CD/ETB complexes.

Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) is one of the most fatal transmissible diseases widespread all over the world. It is caused by a type of bacteria known as mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB), which is highly contagious through airborne transmission, that includes tiny droplets produced by coughs and sneezes. Although the bacteria mainly target the lungs, there are high possibilities of them attacking other parts of the body if left untreated ^[1]. According to the annual report from World Health Organization (WHO) for year 2019, TB was classified as one of the top 10 causes of death in the world, where around 10 million people were infected, and 14% of the people did not manage to survive ^[2].

Among the first-line treatment for combating TB include the use of combination of various drugs as shown in Figure 1, namely rifampicin (RFP), isoniazid (INH), pyrazinamide (PZA) and ethambutol (ETB) in certain dosage, as to effectively get rid of the bacteria while preventing antibiotic resistance to a particular drug ^[3]. However, the main emphasis of this research is specifically on INH and ETB, as they are commonly prescribed together for prolonged treatment of TB even in the initial phase. To simplify, INH helps to reduce the division of MTB in the body by inhibiting the synthesis of mycolic acid, while ETB works by hindering the production of an enzyme called arabinosyl transferase, where both components mentioned are essential elements required in the biosynthesis process of bacteria cell wall ^[4,5]. Generally, the recommended dosage for both INH and ETB are around 10-25 mg/kg of human weight per day, which varies according to the severity of infection ^[6,7]. Since the dosage is considered relatively high, long-term intake of these drugs may lead to adverse drug reactions and side effects, which include hepatitis, dermatitis, and neurotoxicity related effects such as loss of vision and color blindness ^[8]. Hence, it is necessary to improve drug delivery systems

for prolonged TB treatment, to minimize the occurrence of harmful side effects that contribute to increased deterioration of the patient's body.

Figure 1. First line anti-TB drugs ^[9].

At present, it is a known fact that supramolecular macrocycles are useful mediums used in drug delivery systems to enhance drug stability, solubility, targeting, and stimuli responsiveness, with the goal of reducing dosage and dosing frequency by upgrading the therapeutic benefits ^[10]. This unique method is more often introduced as host-guest chemistry, whereby desired drugs are accommodated by hydrophilic macrocycle hosts, for instance, crown ethers, porphyrins, pillar[n]arenes, calix[n]arenes, cucurbiturils, cyclodextrins, and rotaxanes ^[11]. With that said, cyclodextrins (CDs) inclusion complexes have proven their usefulness across wide variety of industries, with greater dominance in food processing and pharmaceutical industries ^[12]. With regards to drug delivery systems, complexation of drugs with CDs reduces the hydrophobicity of poorly soluble drugs, thus increasing the dissolution rate and boosting the absorption by human body. As this positive pharmacological effect happens, the local concentration of drugs administered can be lowered, which is the main purpose of modifying it ^[13].

As seen in Figure 2, typical CDs can be classified into D-(+)-glucopyranose monomers ranging from six to eight units in a ring interconnected by α -1,4-linkages, which are labelled α -, β -, and γ -CD, respectively. However, α -CD has limited cavity space which is deemed unfitting to accommodate most drugs while γ -CD is relatively pricy, which is not a cost-effective option for mass production. As a result, β -CD has always been the top pick when it comes to modification of drug delivery systems [14]. Although the field of CDs-drug inclusion complexes has been explored since decades ago, it is mostly revolving around binary systems, where only a type of desired drug undergoes complexation with the host CDs molecule. This situation has gained the interest of researchers nowadays in exploring similar complexes, but with ternary systems instead. However, the ternary components used are usually additives, natural or synthetic polymers, and solubilizing agents which aid to improve the CDs-drug complexation or the drug-release process, without being directly involved in the host-guest reaction itself [15].

Figure 2. Structures of α -, β -, and γ -CD.

Therefore, the purpose of this research work was to perform complexation of host β -CD molecule with two kinds of first-line TB drugs simultaneously, which are INH and ETB. The synthesized β -CD/INH/ETB ternary inclusion complex was characterized using various advance spectroscopic methods to confirm the penetration of both drug molecules into β -CD cavity, and to investigate its thermal properties, crystallinity, as well as changes in surface

morphology. Additionally, molecular dynamics (MD) and molecular docking simulations were also performed to illustrate the molecular interactions involved between β -CD, INH, and ETB during complexation process.

Results and Discussion

(a) Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)

β -CD/INH binary inclusion complex

Figure 3 shows the FT-IR spectra for β -CD, INH, and β -CD/INH. The absorption bands of β -CD were reported at 3383 cm^{-1} (O-H stretching), 2928 cm^{-1} (C-H stretching), 1419 cm^{-1} (O-H bending), and 1030 cm^{-1} (C-O stretching). Meanwhile, INH had its characteristic bands at 3111 cm^{-1} (N-H stretching), 1666 cm^{-1} (C=O stretching), 1555 cm^{-1} (N-H bending), and 1332 cm^{-1} (C-N stretching). For the β -CD/INH inclusion complex, the vibrational absorption bands were largely dominated by that of β -CD due to it being the most abundant component during complex synthesis. Furthermore, β -CD possesses multiple polar functional groups, such as C-O and O-H which are known to give relatively strong IR absorption bands [16].

The O-H stretching, C-H stretching, O-H bending, and C-O stretching of β -CD were retained with very minimal shifts at 3370 cm^{-1} , 2927 cm^{-1} , 1422 cm^{-1} and 1033 cm^{-1} respectively, whereas the C=O stretching, N-H bending, and C-N stretching of INH were inherited at 1665 cm^{-1} , 1548 cm^{-1} , and 1334 cm^{-1} respectively. The broad O-H stretching band with strong intensity had overlapped with C-N stretching band of INH, which had caused it to disappear. There were no new absorption bands identified in the β -CD/INH spectrum, which had cancelled out the possibility of formation of new bonds [17]. Hence, the appearance of characteristic peaks of both β -CD and INH in the β -CD/INH spectrum had indicated successful formation of the binary inclusion complex.

Figure 3. FT-IR spectra of (a) β -CD, (b) INH, and (c) β -CD/INH.

β -CD/ETB binary inclusion complex

As shown in Figure 4, ETB had displayed its characteristic peaks at 3345 cm^{-1} (O-H stretching), 2973 cm^{-1} and 2830 cm^{-1} (C-H stretching), and 1028 cm^{-1} (C-N stretching). Although like the case of β -CD/INH where the absorption bands of β -CD were also predominant in the spectrum of β -CD/ETB, there were slight differences which had made it distinguishable from the pure components. First, the absorption peak at 3347 cm^{-1} corresponding to O-H stretching of β -CD and ETB had significantly broadened especially when compared to the narrow peak of pure ETB, which was highly likely due to the combination of O-H functional groups of both pure components. Next, the twin absorption peaks of C-H stretching which belonged to ETB were retained with slight shifts at 2925 cm^{-1} and 2838 cm^{-1} , which had overlapped with the C-H stretching peak associated with β -CD, causing it to be unnoticeable from the β -CD/ETB spectrum. Meanwhile, the O-H bending, and C-O stretching which belonged to β -CD were found at 1426 cm^{-1} and 1031 cm^{-1} respectively.

As compared to the pure components, the mentioned C-O stretching peak had broadened and coincidentally overlapped with the C-N stretching of ETB at 1031 cm^{-1} . These observations had provided useful evidence to show the encapsulation of ETB into the β -CD cavity.

Figure 4. FT-IR spectra of (a) β -CD, (b) ETB, and (c) β -CD/ETB.

β -CD/INH/ETB ternary inclusion complex

Since the synthesis of β -CD/INH and β -CD/ETB had given positive outcomes based on the results obtained from FT-IR analysis, the exact same synthesis method was used to synthesize β -CD/INH/ETB ternary inclusion complex. As shown in Figure 5, it was surprisingly observed that the absorption bands showed little to no similar features to both the pure drugs encapsulated in β -CD. In other words, the very intense β -CD absorption bands had completely concealed the absorption bands of INH and ETB. However, this was not considered as a rare occurrence, given that a few literatures had recorded similar results. There was research on encapsulation of guava leaf oil in hydroxypropyl-beta-cyclodextrin (HP β -CD), and it was found that that absorption bands of guava leaf oil had completely disappeared in the

spectrum of the complex ^[18]. Other than that, Wang et al. had performed FT-IR analysis on β -CD/soybean lecithin inclusion complex, and it was observed that the absorption bands of soybean lecithin were completely covered by that of β -CD ^[19]. Likewise, Liu et al. had also reported the disappearance of characteristic peaks of β -caryophyllene upon complexation with β -CD ^[20]. Therefore, the encapsulation of INH and ETB into β -CD was not deemed unsuccessful as alternative characterization methods can be used.

Figure 5. FT-IR spectra of (a) β -CD, (b) ETB, (c) INH (green), and (d) β -CD/INH/ETB.

(b) Proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (¹H-NMR) and 2-dimensional nuclear Overhauser effect spectroscopy (2D-NOESY)

¹H-NMR study of β -CD, INH, and ETB

As the results obtained from FT-IR alone may not be sufficient to prove complex formation and elucidate the structure of synthesised complex, ¹H-NMR serves as a reliable way to provide more useful information regarding the molecular interaction between β -CD and the desired drugs. When a guest molecule enters the hydrophobic cavity of β -CD, there will be

observable changes of chemical shift in the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra ^[21]. As shown in Figure 6, the affected protons will generally be H3 or H5, where both are in the β -CD inner cavity ^[22]. As for the OH groups on the β -CD edges, there are possibilities of hydrogen bond formation with the guest drug molecules, which will be further discussed in the simulation section.

Figure 6. (a) chair conformation and (b) conical structure of β -CD with H numbering ^[22]

Figures 7 – 9 show the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of the pure components that made up the binary complexes β -CD/INH, β -CD/ETB, and ternary complex β -CD/INH/ETB. In this research work, the difference in chemical shifts of the protons involved upon complexation in each component are calculated using equation (1):

$$\Delta\delta = \delta (\text{complex}) - \delta (\text{pure component}) \quad (1)$$

and the induced shifts are labelled with negative and positive signs which denote upfield and downfield shifts, respectively. For the ease of discussion, the six types of protons in β -CD are classified as H1 – H6 as shown in Figure 7, four types of protons in INH are Ha – Hd as shown in Figure 8, while the six types of protons in ETB are H(i) – H(vi) as shown in Figure 9. With that said, the characterisation was mainly focused on β -CD/INH/ETB ternary inclusion complex as FT-IR method was not able to prove its successful formation.

Figure 7. ^1H -NMR spectrum of pure β -CD.

Figure 8. ^1H -NMR spectrum of pure INH.

Figure 9. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of pure ETB.

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ study of $\beta\text{-CD/INH/ETB}$ ternary inclusion complex

Figure 10 shows the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of $\beta\text{-CD/INH/ETB}$ ternary inclusion complex, along with appropriate proton labelling mentioned previously, while Figure 11 shows the magnified version of the same figure specifically at 3.0 – 4.0 ppm, for the ease of interpretation due to excessive number of overlapping peaks. From the spectra, it can be said that all the characteristic peaks of $\beta\text{-CD}$ (H1 – H6), and that of ETB (H(i) – H(vi)) were successfully identified. However, the H2 – H6 peaks of $\beta\text{-CD}$ were found to have overlapped and partially merged with H(iv) and H(vi) peaks of ETB due to them possessing chemical shifts very close to one another. With relation to INH, the Hd peak which was supposed to appear at ~ 4.6 ppm had disappeared, only Ha – Hc peaks were observed.

For the case of disappearance of Hd peak in the ternary complex, it was likely due to amine (N-H) group possessing an exchangeable proton, which was known to give broad signals that may or may not diminish and disappear in the NMR spectrum if the concentration is relatively low among other components ^[23]. Additionally, two solvent peaks were found in the spectrum of the ternary complex. The sharp peak at ~2.5 ppm was attributed to DMSO-d₆, while the peak at ~1.0 ppm was deduced to be from CH₃ proton of ethanol. The reason ethanol peak appeared in the spectrum was most probably due to the use of this solvent during the preparation of complex, where it may not have evaporated completely during drying process. The chemical shifts of each proton involved in inclusion complexation are recorded in Table 1.

Figure 10. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of $\beta\text{-CD/INH/ETB}$.

Figure 11. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of $\beta\text{-CD/INH/ETB}$ (magnified at 3.0 – 4.0 ppm).

Table 1. Chemical shifts (ppm) corresponding to β -CD, INH, ETB, and β -CD/INH/ETB.

Proton	β CD	Isoniazid	Ethambutol	Ternary	
				complex	Induced shift
H1	4.8237	-	-	4.8182	-0.0055
H2	3.2969	-	-	3.2989	+0.0020
H3	3.6449	-	-	3.6542	+0.0093 ^[*]
H4	3.3437	-	-	3.3405	0.0032
H5	3.5540	-	-	3.5556	+0.0016
H6	3.6394	-	-	3.6383	+0.0011
H _a	-	10.1003	-	10.1189	+0.0186 ^[*]
H _b	-	8.6983	-	8.6928	-0.0055
H _c	-	7.7233	-	7.7183	-0.0050
H _d	-	4.6228	-	-	-
H(i)	-	-	0.9259	0.9220	-0.0039
H(ii)	-	-	1.6228	1.6448	+0.0220 ^[*]
H(iii)	-	-	3.0586	3.0720	+0.0134 ^[*]
H(iv)	-	-	3.5756	3.5720	-0.0036
H(v)	-	-	5.3804	5.3926	+0.0122 ^[*]
H(vi)	-	-	3.3221	3.3249	+0.0028

[*]The most significant chemical shifts among other protons upon complexation.

From Table 1, it can be observed that every proton in the pure components had experienced slight to relatively large chemical shifts upon inclusion complexation to form the ternary complex. This phenomenon could be inferred as the result of deshielding effect of guest drug protons along with the shielding effect of host β -CD when host-guest molecular interactions occur ^[24]. Within expectations, the H3 proton of β -CD had significantly larger

chemical shift when compared to the rest of its protons. Since H3 is in the β -CD inner cavity, this observation could be suggesting the penetration of drug molecules into the host cavity. Nevertheless, the Ha associated to amine group of INH, as well as aliphatic H(ii), aliphatic H(iii) and amine H(v) of ETB had notably larger chemical shifts in comparison with the other protons. To account for this situation, it can be said that certain kinds of intermolecular interaction, for instance hydrophobic interaction, van der Waals, and hydrogen bonding had occurred between β -CD, INH, and ETB, specifically at the position of the five protons [25].

Even though most peaks of the pure components were identified through $^1\text{H-NMR}$ characterization, there were still possibilities that the ternary complex may not be a stable product, as the synthesized complex in the aqueous-state may not exist as the same complex in the solid-state [26]. Therefore, other characterization methods ought to be performed to complement the results obtained in this section, to determine whether the desired ternary complex had been formed.

2D-NOESY NMR study of β -CD/INH/ETB ternary inclusion complex

Figure 12 shows the 2D-NOESY NMR spectrum of β -CD/INH/ETB. With reference to the chemical shifts obtained from the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum, there was a correlation between the H3 proton from β -CD at ~ 3.65 ppm and the H(iii) proton from ETB at ~ 3.07 ppm, in which the pair of cross peaks were identified and highlighted with red boxes. The observed cross peaks had signified the successful penetration of ETB moiety into the hydrophobic cavity of β -CD. However, the other protons that may have been involved in complexation reaction according to $^1\text{H-NMR}$ results were not identifiable in 2D-NOESY spectra due to the lack of other observable pair of cross peaks.

Figure 12. 2D-NOESY NMR spectrum of β -CD/INH/ETB.

(c) Thermal analysis (TGA)

Comparison between pure components and ternary inclusion complex

As shown in Figure 13, comparison was made between thermograms of the pure components and the synthesised ternary complex on the same plot. Although the ternary complex had begun its decomposition at a lower temperature than that of pure β -CD, this temperature was an intermediate between the decomposition temperature of both drugs (β -CD/INH/ETB: 239.63°C, β -CD: 311.77°C INH: 211.26°C, ETB: 255.89°C). Moreover, the ternary complex had significantly lower total weight loss as compared to every pure component (β -CD/INH/ETB: 83.52%, β -CD: 97.88%, INH: 99.45%, ETB: 99.19%). This observation had proven that the overall thermal stability of ternary complex was greater than that of pure components, as the exact same range of temperature applied was not able to decompose the

complex completely [21]. Besides, the ternary complex had lower percentage of water loss than that of pure β -CD, which signified that partial water molecules were displaced to create space for both guest drug molecules to enter the β -CD cavity during host-guest complexation (β -CD/INH/ETB: 11.26%, β -CD: 13.75%) [27].

Figure 13. TGA thermogram for β -CD, INH, ETB, and β -CD/INH/ETB.

Comparison between binary and ternary inclusion complexes

Meanwhile, Figure 14 shows the comparison between the thermograms of synthesized binary complexes with the ternary complex. It was observed that the ternary complex suffered water loss at a lower temperature than that of both binary complexes (β -CD/INH/ETB: 61.57°C, β -CD/INH: 75.50°C, β -CD/ETB: 62.17°C). Additionally, the percentage of water loss for the ternary complex was in between the binary complexes (β -CD/INH/ETB: 11.26%, β -CD/INH: 7.77%, β -CD/ETB: 11.54%). Other than that, the ternary complex also decomposed at temperature in between the binary complexes (β -CD/INH/ETB: 239.63°C, β -CD/INH: 309.87°C, β -CD/ETB: 205.17°C). Most importantly, the total weight loss of the

ternary complex was the lowest among the three complexes (β -CD/INH/ETB: 83.52%, β -CD/INH: 95.81%, β -CD/ETB: 92.00%). This had given a strong indication that the synthesized ternary complex was more thermally stable than the binary complexes. Hence, these observations had made it possible to distinguish between the pure components, synthesized binary, and ternary complexes, as each of them possessed their own unique thermal properties.

Figure 14. TGA thermogram for β -CD/INH, β -CD/ETB, and β -CD/INH/ETB.

(d) Surface morphological study (SEM)

Figures 15(a) – (c) show the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of pure β -CD, INH, and ETB respectively. Based on the figures, pure β -CD appeared as bulky, irregular, and shattered cuboid-like structure with imperfect edges. Meanwhile, pure INH had rather smooth surface and regular structure which were distributed in chunks of various dimensions. As for pure ETB, it had irregular, thin, and long strips which were stacked in piles or layers. Figure 15(d) shows the SEM image of β -CD/INH while Figure 15(e) shows that of β -CD/ETB.

It was observed that upon complexation, β -CD/INH had formed a new solid phase with significant reduction in particle size and crystallinity as compared to the pure components. It can also be seen that β -CD/ETB was composed of highly amorphous and homogeneous aggregates of small particle fragments, which was totally different from the pure components.

As for the SEM image of β -CD/INH/ETB ternary complex, it was scanned with double the magnification of the previous samples, as the ternary complex particles were even smaller than that of both binary complexes. Based on Figure 15(f), β -CD/INH/ETB had exhibited a combination of several structures, which include irregular crystalline flakes to amorphous aggregate fragments. Though the particles may not be completely amorphous as expected for typical complex compounds, they had totally different shapes and sizes from the pure components.

Since both binary complexes and the ternary complex had undergone notable surface morphological changes during encapsulation of desired drugs in the β -CD cavity, it can be said that the formation of new solid phases with smaller particles sizes and reduced crystallinity were confirmed. It was not possible to differentiate the individual components based solely on the images, which had indicated the strong host-guest interaction ^[28]. In other words, the synthesis of binary and ternary complexes had resulted in the successful formation of new complexes which were highly distinctive from each other.

Figure 15. SEM images of (a) β -CD, (b) INH, (c) ETB, (d) β -CD/INH, (e) β -CD/ETB, and (f) β -CD/INH/ETB.

(e) **X-ray diffraction (XRD) study**

Previously, it was a known fact that peak intensities were directly proportional to the crystallinity of compound [29]. Hence, as shown in Figure 16, the sharp peaks of INH had confirmed its very strong crystalline form, with characteristic peaks at 2θ diffraction values of 11.9° , 14.3° , 15.6° , 19.6° , 25.3° , 27.2° , 28.7° , 38.7° , and 45.9° . Meanwhile, it was observed that ETB had its characteristic peaks at 13.8° and 15.2° . Only two peaks were mentioned because the rest of the peaks had relatively low intensities which were not significant enough to be taken as reference. Whereas for β -CD, it had characteristic peaks at 10.6° , 12.5° , 15.3° and 22.7° . Based on the overall peak height, the crystallinity of the pure components could be arranged in descending order, from $\text{INH} > \beta\text{-CD} > \text{ETB}$. Within expectation, $\beta\text{-CD}/\text{INH}/\text{ETB}$ exhibited more amorphous character by having reduced peak intensity upon complexation, while retaining the characteristic peaks of β -CD. Since the characteristic peaks of INH and ETB did not make obvious appearance in the XRD pattern of the ternary complex, it was highly likely that both guest drug compounds had entered the β -CD cavity simultaneously [30].

Figure 16. XRD patterns of (a) INH, (b) ETB, (c) β -CD, and (d) β -CD/INH/ETB.

(f) Molecular dynamics (MD) simulation analysis

In order to determine the molecular properties of β -CD, INH, and ETB, MD simulation was carried out and the following analysis such as interaction energy and RDF were discussed below. The optimized structures for pure β -CD, INH, ETB, and pure water were obtained and illustrated in Figure 17. The β -CD structure was position-restrained by a force constant in the simulation box so that INH and ETB would approach its cavity from a desired distance. This could serve as a manipulated variable, whether it be equidistance from both INH and ETB, or having one of the drugs positioned nearer to it before simulation was performed. Simple point charge (SPC) water molecules were used because they were deemed universal and compatible with the GROMOS96 forcefield applied in the system, which did not involve co-parametrization with any commonly used water models [31]. The exact number of water molecules calculated using GROMACS was 884, where they would fit entirely into the simulation box of the chosen size.

Figure 17. Optimized structure of (a) β -CD, (b) INH, (c) ETB, and (d) pure water.

Simulation of binary inclusion complexes

The simulation of both β -CD/INH and β -CD/ETB were done in an explicit water-filled environment. The solvation process was done by inserting the maximum number of SPC water molecules into the simulation box after packing β -CD and the desired drug. This step was taken to represent any type of solvent used to prepare the binary complexes through the synthesis method chosen, which was solvent evaporation. The main justifications of performing MD simulation for β -CD/INH and β -CD/ETB were to verify the differences between the stability of synthesized binary complexes and ternary complex, as well as observing their unique binding modes and selectivity of β -CD towards INH or ETB during complexation. The structures of β -CD/INH and β -CD/ETB by simulation are illustrated in Figure 18. The interaction and binding energy of β -CD/INH, β -CD/ETB, and β -CD/INH/ETB inclusion complexes are tabulated in Table 2, expressed in the unit of kcal/mol. From precise calculations, the interaction energy of β -CD/INH (-36.4236 kcal/mol) was slightly negative than that of β -CD/ETB (-36.3997 kcal/mol).

Figure 18. MD predicted structure of (a) β -CD/INH (side view) (b) β -CD/INH (top view), (c) β -CD/ETB (side view), and (d) β -CD/ETB (top view).

Table 2. Interaction energies of β -CD/INH and β -CD/ETB and β -CD/INH/ETB by MD.

Complexes	Interaction energy [kcal/mol]	Binding energy [kcal/mol]
β -CD/INH	-36.4236	36.4236
β -CD/ETB	-36.3997	36.3997
β -CD/INH/ETB	-132.8123	132.8123

Simulation of ternary inclusion complex

For the simulation of β -CD/INH/ETB, initially it was performed by packing β -CD simultaneously with INH and ETB in the same simulation box. However, it was found in several trials that both drugs were not able to enter the β -CD cavity at the same time after carrying out the simulation, where only INH or ETB alone reacted with β -CD while leaving the other drug outside of the cavity. Therefore, another approach was utilized, which was reacting β -CD with one of the drugs before reacting with another. Although such an approach was slightly more time-consuming, the simulation was deemed successful when β -CD was allowed to react with INH initially forming a binary inclusion complex. The structure was then packed with ETB into the simulation box forming a ternary inclusion complex.

The complex was analyzed in terms of the presence of various covalent molecular bonding, including hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions. Hence, the optimized structure of β -CD/INH/ETB and the possible molecular interactions between components within the cavity are illustrated in Figure 19. According to the literature, it was made clear that

a typical hydrogen bond length could range from 2.8 – 3.0 Å, and in some uncommon cases, it could be extended further and rupture beyond 3.5 Å, in which it would turn into ordinary dipole-dipole interactions [32].

The interaction energy of β -CD/INH/ETB complex was calculated as shown in Table 2. The inclusion of both INH and ETB molecules inside β -CD rim enhanced the stability of the complex compared to each binary inclusion (β -CD/INH and β -CD/ETB). This suggested that the synthesized ternary inclusion complex could form a more stable complex than both binary inclusions. Since both binary complexes and the ternary complex had positive binding energies, it can be concluded that the formation of all three complexes did not occur spontaneously, external energy is required to separate the host-guest molecules in the inclusion complexes [33].

Figure 19. MD predicted structures of β -CD/INH/ETB (a) view 1, and (b) view 2.

Radial distribution function (RDF) for binary and ternary inclusion complexes

The radial distribution functions (RDF) was conducted to give a clearer picture on the interaction of β -CD with INH or ETB as plotted in Figures 20 and 21. From the figures, it can be observed that the RDF curve of β -CD/INH had a sharper and taller peak than β -CD/ETB. This meant that the INH preferred locate closer to β -CD cavity compared to ETB. Considering

the longer straight chain and larger molecular size of ETB compared to INH, these observations were self-explanatory as INH could penetrate β -CD cavity more easily with its smaller molecular size. Nevertheless, the broader RDF curve of β -CD with ETB may also indicate weaker molecular interaction of β -CD with ETB [34]. Another possible reason was due to steric hindrance, since there were three molecules involved in the complexation reaction [35]. From Figure 22, a similar trend was observed in β -CD/INH/ETB inclusion where β -CD/INH showed dominant interaction compared to β -CD/ETB.

Figure 20. RDF for the distance between β -CD and INH in β -CD/INH.

Figure 21. RDF for the distance between β -CD and ETB in β -CD/ETB.

Figure 22. RDF for the distance between β -CD and INH, β -CD and ETB in β -CD/INH/ETB.

(g) Molecular docking simulation

From molecular docking results, the calculated binding energies and hydrogen bonds of β -CD/INH and β -CD/ETB complexes were tabulated in Table 3. Binding energy was used to determine the stability of the structures after the complexation. For docking, the more negative value of binding energy means the higher stability of the complex. As shown in Table 3, the β -CD structure forms the most stable complex towards INH molecules having a binding energy of -4.63 kcal/mol which was slightly negative than β -CD/ETB complex (-3.60 kcal/mol). The hydrogen bonding was observed to be found in both complexes. It was interesting to notice that even though β -CD/ETB complex has lower binding energy than the β -CD/INH complex, there are four hydrogen bonds; H7 – O25 (1.8 Å), H8 – O3 (2.2 Å), H23 – O8 (2.1 Å), and H24 – O3 (2.1 Å), from the ETB molecule that interacts with oxygen of β -CD molecule.

To get a better view of the interactions between the molecules, the lowest energy conformations are depicted in Figure 23. It was notably shown that only one hydrogen from

INH (H5) interacts with oxygen from β -CD while four hydrogen from ETB (H7, H8, H23, H24) interact with oxygen from β -CD molecules. The results obtained had similar trend with MD simulation where the β -CD/INH complex had higher binding energy than β -CD/ETB complex. Despite the differences in binding energy values obtained between β -CD/INH and β -CD/ETB, both INH and ETB were considered to form stable structures with β -CD.

Table 3. The calculated binding energies and hydrogen bonds of β -CD/INH and β -CD/ETB complexes by docking.

Complexes	Binding energies, ΔG_{bind} [kcal/mol]	Hydrogen bond [Å]
β -CD/INH	-4.63	H5 – O15 (2.0)
β -CD/ETB	-3.60	H7 – O25 (1.8) H8 – O3 (2.2) H23 – O8 (2.1) H24 – O3 (2.1)

Figure 23. The lowest energy conformation of docking structures of (a) β -CD/INH, and (b) β -CD/ETB complexes.

Conclusion

The present work had successfully verified the formation of β -CD/INH/ETB ternary inclusion complex using FT-IR, $^1\text{H-NMR}$, 2D-NOESY NMR, TGA, SEM, and XRD. The evidence provided from all the characterization methods were meant to complement each other, not to be considered as standalone. Positive outcomes were obtained for all methods, except for FT-IR where there were no significant changes observed in the spectra, but with justifications given. The molecular interactions revolving around the components that made up the ternary inclusion complex were also studied using MD simulation and docking to give a better understanding of the complexation process, along with the interaction and binding energies of the complex. Therefore, it is believed that this research work had provided sufficient evidence to serve as a preliminary work, in which such method of improving bioavailability of fixed dose drug combinations (FDCs) of INH and ETB can be further explored for the well-being of TB patients.

Experimental Section

Materials

β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) and isoniazid (INH) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, USA. Ethambutol hydrochloride (ETB) was purchased from Cayman Chemical Company, USA. All three pure components were directly used without further purification. Ethanol (95%, AR grade) was purchased from Qrec, Malaysia. Dimethyl sulfoxide- d_6 (DMSO- d_6) (99.8%, NMR grade) was purchased from MagniSolv, Switzerland. Distilled water was available in the laboratory and used for dilution of solvents whenever necessary.

Instrumentations

For the characterization procedures in this research, some equipment was utilized. The Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectrometer (Spectrum 2000) was obtained from Perkin Elmer, USA. Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectrometer (Avance III, 500 MHz) was obtained from Bruker, Germany. Thermogravimetric (TGA) analyser (SDTA851e) was obtained from Mettler Toledo, USA. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) (S-3400N) was obtained from Hitachi, Japan. X-ray diffractometer (XRD) (D8 DISCOVER) was also obtained from Bruker, Germany. Weighing balance (AUW220D) was obtained from Shimadzu, Japan.

(a) Preparation of β -CD/INH, β -CD/ETB, and β -CD/INH/ETB complexes

Solvent evaporation method was chosen to prepare β -CD/INH/ETB ternary inclusion complex. β -CD, INH and ETB were weighed in molar ratio of 2:1:1, followed by addition of small amount of ethanol, and continuously stirred until the mixture is completely dissolved (temperature could be slightly increased if undissolved). After obtaining the mixture solution, it was filtered and dried under fume hood or an oven with moderate temperature to remove the solvent. Then, the dried products were stored in a desiccator under vacuum to achieve constant weight, and finally kept in an airtight container. The above steps were repeated to prepare binary inclusion complexes of β -CD/INH and β -CD/ETB, with molar ratios of 1:1, for comparison purposes during characterization.

(b) Characterization of synthesized complexes and pure components

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)

The formation of synthesized complexes was evaluated based on the observed changes in FT-IR peak positions, shapes, and intensities. The spectra for pure samples of β -CD, INH, and ETB, along with the binary complexes β -CD/INH, β -CD/ETB, and ternary complex β -CD/INH/ETB were recorded using potassium bromide (KBr) method, where the sample and KBr pellets were grinded and mixed in a ratio of 1:3, with the use of mortar and pestle. The spectra were scanned in the full range of 400 – 4000 cm^{-1} , with a resolution of 8 cm^{-1} .

Proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy ($^1\text{H-NMR}$) and 2-dimensional nuclear Overhauser effect spectroscopy (2D-NOESY)

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ was used to examine the formation of synthesized complexes through the calculation of peak chemical shift difference in the spectra. The pure samples of β -CD, INH, and ETB, along with the binary complexes β -CD/INH, β -CD/ETB, and ternary complex β -

CD/INH/ETB were dissolved separately beforehand in deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO- d_6) before characterization. The spectra were acquired with a frequency of 600 MHz, and the chemical shifts were recorded in terms of parts per million (ppm). The characterization steps were followed by obtaining 2D-NOESY spectrum of β -CD/INH/ETB, as additional evidence to support the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ results.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

TGA analysis was done to study the weight loss profile for the pure components and synthesized complexes. The pure samples of β -CD, INH, and ETB, along with the binary complexes β -CD/INH, β -CD/ETB, and ternary complex β -CD/INH/ETB were weighed separately between 5 – 10 mg using aluminum crucible and were heated from ambient temperature to 900 °C in N_2 atmosphere, at a constant heating rate of 10 °C min^{-1} .

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron microscope was utilized to detect the change in surface morphology before and after the formation of synthesized complexes. The scans were run at an accelerating voltage of 5 – 10 kV, at magnifications of 500 – 5000 \times for the pure samples of β -CD, INH, and ETB, along with the binary complexes β -CD/INH, β -CD/ETB, and ternary complex β -CD/INH/ETB, without any further treatments.

X-ray diffraction (XRD)

XRD study was employed to assess the changes in diffraction patterns and intensities before and after the formation of synthesized complexes in the single crystal state. The diffractograms of pure samples of β -CD, INH, and ETB, along with the binary complexes β -CD/INH, β -CD/ETB, and ternary complex β -CD/INH/ETB were obtained in the scan range of

10 – 70°, and step size of 0.02°, with diffractometer operating at voltage of 40 kV and current of 40 mA.

(c) Study of molecular interaction using molecular dynamics (MD) simulation

To understand how the molecules interact with each other during complex formation, MD simulations were performed by GROMACS package (version 4.5). The optimized structure of β -CD, INH, and ETB, respectively, were extracted from the huge repository of Automated Topology Builder (ATB). All three molecules were packed in a $3.0 \times 3.0 \times 3.0$ nm virtual simulation box, with β -CD placed at the center of the box, position restrained with force constant of 100 000 kJ mol⁻¹ and were surrounded by maximum amount of simple point charge (SPC) water molecules. To represent the actual interaction potential between β -CD, INH, and ETB, the GROMOS molecular force fields were applied within the simulation box. The integration step was set to be 1.0 fs throughout, non-bonded interactions were computed up to 1.2 nm, while the Particle Mesh Ewald (PME) was applied within a spacing of 1.2 nm and fourth-order interpolation. To simulate the bond formation approach, the searching range of neighboring molecule was pre-set to be 1.2 nm and would be updated for every five steps taken, where the bonds formed were restricted using fourth-order linear constraint solver (LINCS) algorithm. Meanwhile, V-rescale temperature and Parrinello-Rahman pressure control were both applied in the thermodynamic system. For its parameter, the temperature coupling constant was set as 0.1 ps, isothermal compressibility for pressure was set as 4.5×10^{-5} , reference pressure was set as 1.013 atm, and the relaxation time for the system was 2.0 ps.

The system went through energy minimization process with 100,000 steps of steepest descent followed by the same number of steps of conjugate gradients. The canonical ensemble (NVT) and isobaric-isothermal ensemble (NPT) were introduced into the system before

equilibrium was reached, whereby INH and ETB travelled towards the internal cavity of β -CD, forming a ternary inclusion complex of β -CD/INH/ETB. All the above steps were repeated to simulate the formation of β -CD/INH and β -CD/ETB binary inclusion complexes, where the individual molecules were packed in the exact same virtual simulation box. For the ease of calculation for interaction energies, simulations were also performed for pure molecules of β -CD, INH, ETB, and water. Equations (2) and (3) were used to calculate the binding energy of the binary and ternary systems:

$$E_{(\text{interaction})} = E_{(\beta\text{-CD}/\text{drug}/\text{water})} - [E_{(\beta\text{-CD})} + E_{(\text{drug})} + E_{(\text{water})}] \quad (2)$$

$$E_{(\text{binding})} = - E_{(\text{interaction})} \quad (3)$$

As shown in the equations above, the interaction energy of the system was calculated by subtracting the sum of individual interaction energy of the pure drug components from the interaction energy of the simulated binary or ternary complex, followed by converting the value into negative to obtain the final binding energy, expressed in the unit of kcal/mol.

(c) Molecular docking simulation

To determine the binding energy and binding affinity of β -CD/INH and β -CD/ETB, molecular docking simulation was performed by using the AutoDock 4.2 software package [36]. All molecules were prepared and saved in the file in PDBQT format. All parameters used in the calculation were taken by default from the software. To locate the possible binding sites of INH and ETB molecules towards BCD, a 40 x 40 x 40 (x, y, z) three-dimensional grid box with a center distance of 0.375 Å was generated sufficiently to cover the whole of the β -CD molecule. In the docking procedure, the macromolecule of β -CD was kept as a rigid structure while the INH or ETB molecule each was set as a flexible structure that moved around the vicinity of the grid box set up for the β -CD molecule. Then, the Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm

(LGA) ^[37] from MGLTools, was used to determine the appropriate binding and configuration modes of the β -CD/INH and β -CD/ETB.

Supporting Information Summary

Additional figures and tables related to experimental data in Results and Discussion are displayed within the Supporting Information.

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Keywords

Antituberculosis, Cyclodextrins, Ethambutol, Host-guest systems, Isoniazid

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Table of Contents

Cyclodextrins (CDs) are useful to enhance drug properties while providing many therapeutic benefits. Despite the great extent on research for CDs-drug ternary inclusion complexes, most of the ternary components added were multi-functional polymer molecules that aid in improving speed and efficiency of complex formation. Hence, this research work has explored the possibility of formation of CDs-drug ternary complex with two kinds of antituberculosis drug molecules simultaneously, namely isoniazid (INH) and ethambutol (ETB).